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SENSITIVITY OF THE INVESTOR'S TOWARDS STOCK MARKET INVESTMENT

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ABSTRACT

Investment in stock market has become a common phenomenon for all the individuals. The growth of stock market contributes to national economic growth only when this growth translates into increased mobilization of resources, return from investment, and minimizing the risk attached to stock market investment. This survey has been conducted to find out the stock market investment pattern and risk diversification of retail equity investors. A well structured questionnaire which is pilot tested is utilized to collect the data from investors. The study is restricted to Chennai city alone. The investors are selected randomly with the aid of stock broking firms. The analysis is divided into two parts. The profiles of the investors are examined through percentage analysis and in the second part their perception towards the reason for investment in stock market. The scrutiny of the perception exhibits the main reason for investment in stock market is Return on Investment, liquidity and tax benefits. The technological development, the ease of marketing and trading are not under the main purview of their decisions. The strategy adopted to eliminate or minimize their stock market investment risks are risk diversification, avoiding investment in risk area and portfolio investment. The policy makers and the corporate should give importance for the findings of the study and consider the priority of the investors before taking any major decision.

Key words: Sensitivity, Investors, Stock Market, Investment, Reason for Investment

INTRODUCTION

Investment in stock market has become a common phenomenon for all the individuals. The growth of stock market contributes to national economic growth only when this growth translates into increased mobilization of resources, return from investment, and minimizing the risk attached to stock market investment. In the current scenario, it is pretty evident that the stock market investments are increasing. Diversified investment enables an investor to minimize the risk while maximizing the return for any specific period. The rules and regulations of investment in stock market are comparatively more accessible in the stock market than other types of investment in recent circumstances. Hence today the investors both Indian and international are interested in the Indian stock market as it becomes more attractive with the backup of numerous insurance linked investment schemes with a minimum assured return. Today, the investors keep an eye on all the economic factors to decide about their investment in a specified industry, more specifically on a particular company. After the demonetization, it becomes more reachable as already stock market deals only in online trading through demat account. Therefore, this survey has been conducted to find out the stock market investment pattern and risk diversification of retail equity investors.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Raghavendra Prasad (2016) opines that investors are bullish about the Indian market. The author highlights the fact that rate of return, safety of investment and capital appreciation are very important motives for an investment. Further, the moderate importance of investment is influenced by the liquidity, tax benefits and maturity period. The analysis of the study revealed the fact that there was no significant difference between investors' investment objectives and investors' gender, age and occupation.

Gagan Kukreja (2012) made an attempt to gauge the perception of investors towards Indian capital market with reference to National Capital Region (NCR) investors of India. Through a systematic sampling technique, 120 respondents were analyzed in their study. The variable age significantly influenced the

investment and educational qualification impacted the tax advantage positively. The study further throws light that charges, liquidity and investment attributes are mediating factor for investors' perception.

Naresh Kumar (2010) examined the nature of relationship between the macro economic factors and growth through capital accumulation in India. The study also attempted to investigate the pattern of market capitalization, GDP growth and domestic saving to understand the future direction of the stock market. The study employed mathematical growth function namely Gompertz model to analyze estimation of financial variables and to establish the link between these variables, assuming that financial variables were inter-related. Pearson correlation method was used. The results predicted a positive growth of market capitalization for another five years period and positive association between macro indicators and stock market.

Sulaiman D Mohammad et al. (2009) analysed the relationship between macro economic variables and share prices in Karachi Stock Exchange in Pakistan context. The study considered the quarterly data of economic variables such as foreign exchange rate, foreign exchange reserve, index of industrial production, whole sale price index, gross fixed capital formation and broad money (M2) from 1989 to 2008. The study highlighted that internal factors such as increase in production, whole sale price index and capital formation did not influence stock prices significantly. External factors such as exchange rate and foreign exchange reserves influenced the stock market.

Les Coleman (2007) uses a survey of Australian senior finance executives to examine the influences of personal characteristics and personality traits for an investor's decision making in the face of risk. The test of risk propensity is conducted by means of decision making about whether an investor should chose to invest in options or futures or in secured financial assets. The study revealed that an investor who took the maximum risk earned the maximum returns. The literature on household portfolio choice is vast. The benchmark model, which treats the household as a single agent with constant relative risk aversion, predicts that household portfolio choice was independent of wealth. Yet, empirical evidence suggests that the share of the household portfolio allocated to risky assets increases with wealth. Mazzocco (2004) found that the allocation of resources within the household affects the consumption-investments decision when spouses differ in their preferences.

Various literatures presented bring out the scope for the present research work. Literatures related to the study shows clearly that there are numerous studies on stock market and investors perceptions. An efficient market frame work indicates that well developed stock market efficiently absorbs information. However, there are variations in the analysis of investors' perception depending on the time period and specific economic conditions. This study aims to analyse the perception of investors in Chennai city during the study period.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To examine the demographic profile of the stock market investors.
- To scrutinize the investors perception about the reason for investment in the stock market investment

METHODOLOGY

The perception analysis is based on the primary data. A well structured questionnaire which is pilot tested is utilized to collect the data from investors. The study is restricted to Chennai city alone. The investors are selected randomly with the aid of stock broking firms. The secondary data on stock market are collected from the Reserve Bank of India's Hand Book of Statistics on Indian Economy, Review of Indian Securities market, International Financial Statistics (IFS) database and RBI bulletins.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The study is restricted to investors in the Chennai city.
- The perception analysis cannot be generalized due to the changing dynamics of economic environment.

ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATIONS

The analysis is divided into two parts. The profile of the investors is examined through percentage analysis and in the second part their perception towards the selected economic factors for stock market investment decisions.

Table 1: Age wise distribution of Respondents

Age	No of respondents	Percentage
Below 30	40	16
Between 31 – 50	150	60
Above 50	60	24
Total	250	100

Source: Primary data

Table 1 shows the age wise distribution of respondents. Majority of respondents belongs to age group of 31-50 years because the economic freedom and decision making capacity of individual is high during this middle age group. Only 16 per cent of the investors are young as they do not have good understanding of the stock market investment and its operations during the early years of their career. Generally, the first investment by young people takes the form of bank deposits and insurance policies which need no prior understanding. Younger generations restrict themselves from making investment in share market since basic knowledge and continuous monitoring is necessary for successful investment. Organizing more number of awareness camps and suitable educational programs will attract the youth to invest more in the stock market. Above 50 years age group has risk aversion due to market fluctuation which cautions them to invest only a minimum amount in the stock market

Table 2 : Distribution of Investors based on the Occupation

Occupation	No of Respondents	Percentage
Employed	133	53
Professional	52	21
Business & Others	65	26
Total	250	100

Source: Primary data

The table 2 depicts the fact that majority of the investors are employed either from government and private sectors. Investors who are employed opt for investment in share market. This may be due to the pressure from their peer groups who inspire and encourages them to invest in the stock market. Approximately 21 per cent of the investors belong to the professions like lawyers, auditors, engineers and doctors. Twenty six per cent of the investors belong to business and others categories which include retired persons, students and housewives. Making profit is not the only motive to invest in stock market but also it enables the investor to be a part of the management and allows them to take part in decision making. Hence, more number of awareness programs and subject expert’s dissemination about the stock market investment can be propagated through mass media. This will increase participation in the share market.

Table 3: Income wise distribution of Sample Investors

Income	No of Respondents	Percentage
Below Rs. 20,000	76	30
Rs. 20,000 – Rs. 30,000	137	55
Above Rs. 30,000	37	15
Total	250	100

Source: Primary data

Table 3 exhibits the distribution of investors based on their income. The investment in the stock market is significantly affected by the income earned by the investors. A close scrutiny of the table reveals the fact that 55 per cent of investors belong to the middle income earning group. The predominant participation of wealthy people alone in the stock market has been changed by the entry of the middle class investors after the policy changes of the Government. The investment avenue for a higher earning income groups are more and their preference of investment into the stock market is comparatively lesser than others. Only 30 per cent of the investors belong to the lower income earning group i.e. monthly incomes below Rs. 20,000. This income group spends more on their basic needs and comforts than investing in stock market.

Table 4: Distribution of investors based on the Educational Qualification

Educational qualification	No of Respondents	Percentage
Below HSC	30	12
Under graduate	140	56
Post graduate	80	32
Total	250	100

Source: Primary data

The table 4 portrays the education wise distribution of the investors. Fifty six per cent of them belong to under graduate level while 32 per cent of them are postgraduate level. It shows that only people with higher education make more investment in stock market. It is understood that the educated have much knowledge about the stock market so that they invest more in it. Number of investors below HSC is less because they do not have enough knowledge and their income level also may be less. The awareness about the stock market information is less and hence they are afraid that stock market investment is associated with risk. To create awareness for such group of investors, the regulators may organize special innovative programs through the media.

Table 5: Percentage of Income invested in the share market by the Investors

Percentage of Income invested in the share market	No of Respondents	Percentage
Up to 10%	200	80
11% - 20%	41	16
Above 20%	9	4
Total	250	100

Source: Primary data

The table 5 displays the investors percentage of income invested in the share market. A predominant percentage of investors i.e. 80 per cent of them invest their 10 per cent income in the share market. Investors are ready to invest a small percentage of their income to earn good return, without taking high risk. Only 16 per cent of the investors have the risk taking ability to invest more than 10 per cent of their income in the stock market who may be aware of the techniques and movement of stock market to fetch good return of their investment. Meager percentages of investors alone were interested to invest more than 20 per cent of their income into the stock market. Stock market investment widely attracts the investors as an alternative source to bank deposits and Government savings schemes which yields a low rate of return.

Table 6
Objectives of Stock Market Investment

Income invested in the share market	No of Respondents	Percentage
Regular Dividend	40	16
Liquidity	90	36
Tax benefits	25	10
Capital Investment	95	38
Total	250	100

Source: Primary data

Table 6 exhibits the objective of investing in the stock market. Among the listed objectives, capital appreciation is the most important one which is followed by liquidity and dividend income for investing in the share market. Short term investment in the share market provides the twin benefits of capital appreciation and liquidity. Regular dividend payment is one of the main criterions for fundamental analysis which is not considered as the prime motive for investing in a particular stock. Only 10 per cent of investors prefer to invest in share market mainly for tax benefits. The holding of an investment for a long time attracts both capital appreciation and a good return in the form of dividend.

Table 7
Reason for the investment in the share market

Reason for investment in share market	No of respondents	Percentage
Return on investment	102	41
Liquidity	68	27
Tax benefit	57	23
Efficient market intermediation	11	4
Increased access of trading.	8	3
Any other	6	2

Source: Primary data

The crux of the analysis i.e. reason for the investment in the stock market is presented in a tabular form. The perception of the investors is displayed in descending order for understanding the priority of the investors while investing in the stock market. 41 per cent of the investors substantiate that they invest in the share market mainly for the high return from the investment compared to the other form of investment. Liquidity stands next in the hierarchy for investment with 27 per cent as investors can quickly convert their investments into cash. 23 per cent of investors affirm that the tax benefit is the basis for their investment. The market intermediation efficiency stands next with 4 per cent and a miniscule percentage of the investors cite the other reasons for their investment. The scrutiny of the perception brings to the fore the fact that the main reason for investment in stock market is ROI, Liquidity and tax benefits. The technological development, the ease of marketing and trading are not under the main purview of their decisions. The policy makers and the corporate should give importance to this priority of the investors before taking any major decision.

Table 8
Risks associated with stock market investment

Risks associated with stock market investment	No of respondents	percentage
Risk diversification	118	47
Avoiding investment in risk area	80	32
Portfolio Investment in different industries	52	21

Source: Primary data

The Table 8 lists out the ways in which stock market risks are managed by the investors. Stock market investments are risky investments is a universal fact. Hence it is essential to know how the investors view this risk and what type of strategy they adopt to eliminate or minimize their stock market investment risk is analyzed. Among the different ways of risk management, 118 respondents employ risk diversification as their strategy for making minimal risk investments. Thirty two per cent of the investors select the companies which are blue chip in nature as per the financial intermediaries' advice to avoid any risky investment. Twenty one per cent of the investors prefer portfolio investment which enables them not to be affected by the ups and downs of any one specific industry.

CONCLUSION

The growth of stock market contributes to national economic growth only when this growth translates into increased mobilization of resources, return from investment, and minimizing the risk attached to stock market investment. In the current scenario, it is pretty evident that the stock market investments are increasing. Today, the investors keep an eye on all the environmental and economic factors to decide about their investment in a specified industry, more specifically on a particular company. Therefore, this survey has been conducted to find out the stock market investment pattern and risk diversification of retail equity investors. The scrutiny of the perception brings to the fore the fact that the main reason for investment in stock market is Return on Investment, liquidity and tax benefits. The technological development, the ease of marketing and trading are not under the main purview of their decisions. The strategy adopted to eliminate or minimize their stock market investment risks are risk diversification, avoiding investment in risky area and portfolio investment. The policy makers and the corporate should give importance for the findings of the study and consider the priority of the investors before taking any major decision.

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